

LEGG-CALVE-PERTHES DISEASE**Radut Anastasia,***Student,**Faculty of General Medicine,**State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu",**Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Sandrosean Argentina***scientific supervisor, doctor of medical sciences, associate professor,**State University of Medicine and Pharmacy**"Nicolae Testemitanu", Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

Introduction: Despite the fact that the prevalence of aseptic osteonecrosis of the femoral head is 2.9% of all osteo-muscular disorders and 25% of hip joint disorders [1], this problem requires special attention, while late diagnosis and lack of adequate treatment would could lead to the patient's disability. Because of this, Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is a socially significant pathology [3].

Materials and methods: the statistical retrospective research based on the 30 medical files of patients hospitalized and treated between 01.01.2021 and 31.12.2022, in the section of Pediatric Orthopedics and Traumatology, IMSP Mother and Child Institute from Chisinau , with the diagnosis of Legg-Calve-Perthes disease. Were included in the study patients with idiopathic avascular necrosis confirmed by clinical and radiography signs , age ≤ 18 years old .

Results: According to the statistical retrospective research, 30 children included with LCPD at different stages, of which 19 were male and 11 female, with the maximum represented between 6-10 years (15 child). Patients from the urban environment, presented to the doctor in the first six months after the onset of symptoms , while from the rural in the most cases (12 children) sought medical help more than 6 months. After performing the radiography of the hip joint in each of the children included in the study, it was established that most of hospitalized repeatedly had stage V of the disease (10 children), but primary patients – stage III (3 patients), in 2 cases primary radiography was without pathological changes, and after performing the MRI, was established stage I of the disease.

Conclusions: Legg-Calve-Perthes disease occurred more frequently in children aged between 6-10 years; with a higher incidence among males (1.7:1) and with the prevalence of patients from rural areas (66.7%). Urban patients, who have better and more diverse access to medical assistance, present to the doctor in the first months of illness. Most often primary patients present with stage III of the disease. The most used treatment method is conservative treatment.

Keywords: Legg-Calve-Perthes disease (LCPD) , idiopathic avascular necrosis, aseptic osteonecrosis of the femoral head , hip joint disorders.

Introduction

Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is a self-limiting pathology, characterized by the interruption of the blood supply to the epiphysis of the femoral head, which can lead to its necrosis. LCPD mainly affects children between 2-14 years. Vascular ischemia is temporary, and complete revascularization of the epiphysis occurs in 2-4 years, if the child's age is under 12 years at the onset of the disease. [1]

Worldwide, the prevalence of Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is different and ranges from 0.2 to 19.1 per 100,000 children. The countries of East Asia and the equatorial region have the lowest morbidity; it was found that the incidence of the disease increases with increasing latitude[1]. Boys get sick 4-5 times more often than girls. Usually, the development of the pathological process occurs unilaterally, and bilateral damage occurs in 10% of cases [3].

Nowadays, the main opinion is that Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is caused by a genetic combination with other internal and external factors, having a multifactorial nature [2]. Regardless of the causes of LCPD, the interruption of blood supply in femoral head represents

a main pathogenetic moment that leads to all subsequent pathological changes.

The first manifestation of the disease is usually pain in the hip and limping, may also be present: limitation of movements in the affected hip joint, impotence of the function, fatigue of the muscles of the affected limb. But, nevertheless, Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is devoid of pathognomonic symptoms and has a similarity at the onset of the disease with a number of other diseases of the musculoskeletal system in children. [1,2,3]

Radiography remains the traditional method of diagnosing Legg-Calve-Perthes disease, but it is uninformative in the early stages. In these cases, MRI is used.

Aim

Effectuation of the complex study with reference to the prevalence by sex, by the environment of origin, manifestations, clinical and radiological diagnosis , and treatment in Legg-Calve-Perthes disease in children.

Methods

The study included 30 patients hospitalized and treated between 01.01.2021 and 31.12.2022, in the section of Orthopedics and Pediatric Traumatology, IMSP Mother and Child Institute in Chisinau, with the diagnosis of Legg-Calve-Perthes disease. A statistical study was carried out retrospectively based on the medical files of the patients who were included according to the predetermined criteria. The study inclusion criteria were: patients with idiopathic avascular necrosis confirmed by clinical and radiographic signs, age ≤ 18 years.

Descriptive statistical processing of the data obtained from the observation files was performed in Microsoft Office Excel. The confidentiality of personal data was respected.

Results

During the period of research, among the 30 hospitalized patients, 19 (63.3%) were male, and respectively 11 (36.7%) were female (Figure 1). Thus, we observe that the male gender predominates in a ratio of 1,7:1.

Figure 1. Distribution of patients by sex

Idiopathic aseptic osteonecrosis of the femoral head occurs in children of all ages, but with a higher incidence in children aged between 6-10 years (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of cases depending on age groups (%)

During the research of the observation files of the 30 children with Legg-Calve-Perthes disease, it was established that children from the urban environment presented themselves to the hospital faster compared to

those from the rural environment, most likely it is a consequence of low accessibility in rural areas to a medical care system. Thus, from the urban environment 5 patients (representing 16.67%) presented during the

first 3 months and 5 patients (16.67%) in an interval between 3 and 6 months, while in the case of the rural environment 12 children (40%) sought medical help

more than 6 months after the onset of disease symptoms, 5 children (16.67%) presented between 3 and 6 months and only 3 patients (10%) during the first 3 months. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Distribution of patients according to the duration until the presentation to doctor in dependence on the environment of origin.

The clinical picture in the patients in the studied group was dominated by pain in the affected joint in 93.3%, lameness in 80% of patients, limitation of

movements in 66.7%, functional impotence in 40%, pain in the knee joint in 26.7% patients and muscle fatigue in the affected limb in 13.3% (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Distribution of the group of patients by symptoms

During the objective examination of the patients in the studied group, limping was detected in 80% of children, muscle hypertrophy of the affected limb and flexion contracture presents in 73.3%, abduction contracture in 70%, pain syndrome present on palpation in

63.3% of cases, rotation contracture in 60% of children, in 53.3% of children was detected the shortness of the affected limb, and in 40% positive Drehman sign. (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Distribution of the patient group on objective signs

In the research, radiography of the hip joint was performed in each child, after which stage V of the disease was detected in 10 children (33.33%), stage III in 9 children (30%), stage VI in 5 patients (16.67%), stage

IV in 4 children (13.33%) and in 2 children , the X-ray was without changes, and after performing the MRI, they were diagnosed with stage I of the disease. (Figure 6)

Figure 6. Distribution according to the stage of the disease depending on the number of visit

In the research, conservative treatment was applied to all children diagnosed with Legg-Calve-Perthes disease, and surgical treatment was applied to only 7 of them. (Figure 7)

Figure 7. Distribution of the group of patients after the applied treatment

Discussion

Legg-Calve-Perthes disease refers to socially significant diseases, because in the absence of adequate treatment it leads to the development of instability of the hip joint, coxarthrosis and disability, therefore it requires diagnosis and the application of treatment as early as possible.

In the retrospective study, were included 30 patients with aseptic necrosis of the femoral head in different stages, of which 19 were male and 11 female. In the given group of patients, there is a predominance of the male gender. The age of the patients in the research group varied between 0 and 16 years, the period with the maximum occurrence of the disease was represented between 6-10 years.

The children's environment and the length of time until presentation for medical help were two important characteristics analyzed. Thus, it was observed that the patients from the urban environment (10 children), who have better and more diverse access to medical assistance, visited the doctor in the first six months, while the patients from the rural environment (20 children) in the majority cases (12 children) sought medical help more than 6 months after the onset of the disease.

Of the 30 patients included in the study group in the period 2021-2022, after the x-ray of the hip joint was performed on each of them, it was established that most were with stage V of the disease (10 children), of which all were hospitalized repeated and followed systematic conservative treatment, in 9 children, of which 6 children were hospitalized repeatedly and 3 primary, stage III was established, stage VI in 5 patients examined repeatedly after multiple treatments, in 4 children was diagnosed stage IV of Legg-Calve-Perthes disease according to the STEINBERG classification and in 2 children, the radiograph was without pathological changes, and after performing the MRI, was established stage I of the disease.

In the children from the research, the symptoms were practically identical, with minimal variety. Pain in the affected joint was present in 93.3%, lameness in

80% of patients, limitation of movements in 66.7%, functional impotence in 40%, pain in the knee joint of the affected limb in 26.7% patients and muscle fatigue in 13.3%. Thus, the clinical picture is a typical one, but, nevertheless, Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is devoid of pathognomonic symptoms and has a similarity of clinical picture with a number of other musculoskeletal system diseases in children.

During the objective examination of the patients in the studied group, limping was detected in 80% of children, muscle hypotrophy of the affected limb and flexion contracture presents in 73.3%, abduction contracture in 70%, pain syndrome present on palpation in 63.3% of cases, rotation contracture in 60% of children, in 53.3% of children was detected the shortness of the affected limb, and in 40% positive Drehman sign.

Currently, the most used treatment method with good results is conservative treatment, which is aimed at improving the disturbed vascularization of the hip joint, relieving pain, restoring the function of the affected joint and stopping the progression of bone tissue necrosis, and includes bed rest in the first stages, physical therapy, swimming, vitamin therapy. Operative methods are aimed at restoring congruence in the femoral joint and ensuring a complete coverage of the femoral head with the acetabular component, but are used only in severe cases with failure of conservative treatment.

Conclusions

Legg-Calve-Perthes disease occurred more frequently in children aged between 6-10 years; with a higher incidence among males (1.7:1) and with the prevalence of patients from rural areas (66.7%). Urban patients, who have better and more diverse access to medical assistance, present to the doctor in the first months of illness. Most often primary patients present with stage III of the disease. Clinical manifestations in patients with aseptic osteonecrosis of the femoral head are pain in the affected joint, lameness, limitation of movements, functional impotence, pain in the knee

joint and muscle fatigue of the affected limb. But, nevertheless, Legg-Calve-Perthes disease is devoid of pathognomonic symptoms and has a similarity of clinical picture with a number of other musculoskeletal system diseases in children. Imaging diagnosis - radiography of the hip joint, which is carried out in all patients, allows the assessment of the dynamics of the treatment and the determination, as necessary, of the indications for surgical treatment. MRI remains a gold standard for the early stages of the disease. The treatment of LCPD in children aims to prevent juvenile coxarthrosis and is predominantly orthopedic and only in case of decentration of the femoral head and/or the

presence of a cyst in the femoral neck is resorted to surgical treatment. Regular recovery treatment is of great importance in achieving good results.

References

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